

Notas Nomenclaturales / Nomenclatural Notes

***Diegus* nom. nov., a replacement name for the recent described genus *Didacus* Delicado, Machordom and Ramos 2015 (Caenogastropoda, Hydrobiidae) and subsequent new combination *Diegus gasulli* (Boeters, 1981) comb. nov.**

D. Delicado¹, A. Machordom² & M.A. Ramos²

¹Justus Liebig University Giessen, Department of Animal Ecology & Systematics, Heinrich-Buff-Ring 26-32 IFZD-35392, Giessen, Germany. E-mail: didelicado@gmail.com

²Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales. José Gutiérrez Abascal 2, 28006, Madrid, Spain. E-mails: annie@mncn.csic.es, m.ramos@mncn.csic.es

<http://urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:DBBACE96-390E-499A-B651-736DA2253CB1>

Recibido/Received: 16/05/2016; **Aceptado/Accepted:** 19/05/2016; **Publicado en línea/Published online:** 22/06/2016

Cómo citar este artículo/Citation: Delicado, D., Machordom, A. & Ramos, M. A. 2016. *Diegus* nom. nov., a replacement name for the recent described genus *Didacus* Delicado, Machordom and Ramos 2015 (Caenogastropoda, Hydrobiidae) and subsequent new combination *Diegus gasulli* (Boeters, 1981) comb. nov. *Graellsia*, 72(1): e046. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3989/graellsia.2016.v72.170>

Copyright: © 2016 SAM y CSIC. Salvo indicación contraria, todos los contenidos de la edición electrónica de *Graellsia* se distribuyen bajo licencia de uso y distribución Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY) Spain 3.0.

Based on an integration of morphological, molecular and ecological evidences (Delicado *et al.*, 2015), the freshwater gastropod genus *Pseudamnicola* has been recently split into three different genera: (1) *Pseudamnicola s. str.* Paulucci, 1878 with around 60 species distributed throughout much of the Mediterranean islands and peninsulas, (2) *Corrosella* Boeters, 1970 with 13 known species restricted to the Iberian Peninsula and southern France, and (3) *Didacus* Delicado, Machordom and Ramos, 2015, a monospecific genus whose unique (type) species, *Didacus gasulli* (Boeters, 1981), was found at several streams from southeastern Spain and Ibiza island.

Unfortunately, authors were not aware that the name *Didacus* was previously proposed by Collart (1935) to designate a subgenus of the fruit fly genus *Dacus* Fabricius, 1805 (Diptera: Tephritidae), and afterward only a few taxonomic studies have used *Didacus* Collart at genus level (e.g. Hering, 1940, 1941, 1952; Narayanan & Rattan, 1954). Consequently, the name proposed for the new spring snail genus *Didacus* Delicado, Machordom and Ramos, 2015 was not valid when the taxon was

described, since it is a junior homonym. Hence, in order to fulfill the requirements of the Art. 23 of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature, we here propose *Diegus* **nom. nov.** as a replacement name for *Didacus* Delicado, Machordom and Ramos, 2015, named after our good colleague Diego Moreno as mentioned in the original description. Then *Diegus gasulli* (Boeters, 1981) **comb. nov.** becomes the valid name of the type species.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to our colleague Dr. Alonso-Zarazaga for his advise along the preparation of this note.

References

- Collart, A., 1935. Los Dacinae du Congo Belge (Diptera: Trypetidae). *Bulletin du Musée d'Histoire Naturelle de Belgique*, 11(1): 1-45.
- Delicado, D., Machordom, A. & Ramos, M. A., 2015. Effects of habitat transition on the evolutionary patterns of the micro-gastropod genus *Pseudamnicola* (Mollusca, Hydrobiidae).

- Zoologica Scripta*, 44: 403-417. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/zsc.12104>
- Hering, E. M., 1940. Siruna Seva. *Bf Fruchtfliiegen-Kunde*, 1: 1-16.
- Hering, E. M., 1941. Neue Fruchtfliiegen aus dem Ungarischen National Museum (Dipt.). *Annales Historico-Naturales Musei Hungarici*, 34: 66-70.
- Hering, E. M., 1952. Missione biologica Sagan-Omo diretta dal Prof. Edoardo Zavattari, Diptera Trypetidae. *Rivista di Biologia Coloniale Roma*, [1951], 11: 91-99.
- Narayanan, E. S. & Rattan, L., 1954. Controlling mechanism of pupa-tion in *Didacus ciliatus* (Loew) (Diptera). *Indian Journal of Entomology*, 16: 176-188.